

THERAPEUTIC POTENTIAL OF VALLI PANCHAMOOOL IN VARIOUS DISEASES

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ABSTRACT

Suchrutacharya have mentioned the term Mishraka Gana as it consist of two or more dravyas which have a therapeutically similar characteristics. Valli panchamool is one of the mishraka gana in which Root part of Five dravyas are described such as Vidari, Sariva, Rajani, Guduchi and Ajashrungi. Acharya Bhavprakash described the various actions of Valli Panchamool gana dravyas in various diseases like, Raktapitta (Bleeding disorders), Shopha (swelling), Meha (Diabetes), Shukra dosha (Problems related to sperm. Present study is a review to update knowledge on pharmacological properties, thepeutic potential of Valli Panchamool gana on various diseases by their Gunkarma's.

KEYWORDS: Mishrak gana, Valli Panchamool, Gunakarma,

Therapeutic actions.

INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda is a holistic system of medicines where various medicinal plants are described in the treatment of different diseases. These plants are used as a single drug therapy or combination drug therapy. The word “Mishraka Gana” is derived from two words; “Mishraka” means mixture or combination and “Gana” means group. Our ancient Acharayas classified drugs on the basis of similar morphological characters (Aakriti Sadharmya), properties (Guna Sadharmya) and therapeutic uses (Karma Sadharmya) into groups known as Ganas.

Ancient Acharyas described various drugs in combination therapy based on their similar characteristics either as morphologically, therapeutically or using the same part of all drugs called as a Gana. Suchrutacharya given the term Mishraka Gana as it mentioned two or more dravyas which have a therapeutically or morphologically similar characteristics.

Acharya Charaka classified 10 drugs in one single group known as Mahakshaya in Sutrasthana.^[1] Similarly, Acharya Sushruta classified 10-15 drugs in one single group known Gana in Sutrasthana where 37 such ganas were explained.^[2] This combination of the drugs in different groups allows us to easily understand the availability, properties and therapeutic uses of large number of drugs in systematic manner.

Valli panchamool one of the Mishrak gana described by Acharya Sushrut. These Gana includes the plants named Vidari, Sariva, Rajani, Guduchi and Ajashrunji.^[3]

Valli Panchamool.^[4] The roots of five plants having its habit as Valli (climbing plants) are mentioned in this group.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

विदारीसारिवारजनीगुडूच्यो अजशृंगीचेति वल्लीसंज्ञा।

रक्तपित्तहरौ ह्येतौ शोफत्रय विनाशनौ ।

सर्वमेहहरौ चैव शुक्रदोष विनाशनौ ॥ सु.सू.३८

Acharya Sushrut has mentioned to use the roots of five creepers in equal quantity such as:

Table no. 1: Valli Panchamool Dravya.

Sr. No.	Dravya	Latin name	Family	Part used	Picture
1	Vidari	Pueraria tuberosa	Leguminosae	Root	
2	Sariva	Hemidesmus indicus	Asclepiadaceae	Root	

3	Rajani	Rubia cordifolia	Rubiaceae	Root	
4	Guduchi	Tinospora cordifolia	Menispermaceae	Root	
5	Ajashrungi	Gymnema sylvestre	Asclepiadaceae	Root	

Table no. 2: Synonyms of Valli Panchamool dravyas.

Dravya	Vidari	Sariva	Rajani	Guduchi	Ajashrungi
Synonyms	Bhoomikushmanda, Gajavajipriya, Swadukanda, Ikshugandha, Vrushyakanda, Ksheershukla, Payasvini	Ananta, Sphota, Gopi, Gopakanya, Sharadi, Pratanika, Chandana	Manjishtha, Vikasa, Yojanavalli, Jingi, Samanga, Rasayani, Raktanga, Kalameshi	Amruta, Chakrangi, Chandrahasa, Madhuparni, Jwarari, Chhinna, Vayastha	Madhunashini, Meshashrungi, Vishani, Vartika, Tiktadugdha, Bahalanga

Table no. 3: Rasapanchak of Valli Panchamool Dravya.^[5]

Dravya	Vidari	Sariva	Rajani	Guduchi	Ajashrungi
Rasa	Madhur	Madhur, Tikta	Tikta, Kashaya, Madhur	Katu, Tikta	Kashaya, Tikta
Virya	Sheet	Sheet	Ushna	Ushna	Ushna
Vipak	Madhur	Madhur	Katu	Madhur	Katu
Guna	Guru, Snigdha	Guru, Snigdha	Guru, Ruksha	Laghu, Snigdha	Laghu, Ruksha
Karma	Brumhan, Vrushya, Mutral, Svarya, Balya	Shukrakar, Visha nashan	Varnya, Svarakrut	Sangrahi, Balya, Agnidipan	Chakshushya, Kesharanjini, Dipan, Sransana
Doshagnata	Vata-pitta shamak	Tridosahar	Kapha-Pitta shamak	Tridoshaghna	Kapha-Vatashamak

Table no. 4: Chemical constituents and Pharmacological actions of Valli Panchamool Dravya.

Sr. No.	Dravya	Chemical Constituent	Pharmacological action
1	Vidari	<p>The crude tuber extracts of <i>P. tuberosa</i> are known to contain alkaloids, anthracene, anthocyanidins, anthraquinone, glycosides, carbohydrates, catecholic compounds, coumarins, flavonoids, glycosides, hexose sugars, saponins, steroids, terpenoids, and volatile oils^[6] (Ratnam and Venkata Raju, 2009; Rawtal et al., 2019).</p> <p>Apart from puerarin, daidzein, genistein, irisolidone, and biochanin, many more compounds have been identified from <i>P. tuberosa</i>.</p>	<p>Antidiabetic Activity: Studies suggested that chloroform, petroleum ether, ethanol, and aqueous tuber extracts of <i>P. tuberosa</i> confer significant antidiabetic activity in STZ- (50 mg/kg body weight) induced diabetic rats by a single intraperitoneal injection^[7] (Tripathi and Kohli, 2013).</p> <p>Water extract of root of <i>P. tuberosa</i> showed significant inhibition of dipeptidyl peptidase-4 (DPP-IV) that causes an enhanced half-life of active glucagon-like peptide-1 hormone. This hormone regulates glucose-dependent insulin release from β-cells of the pancreas in rats^[8] (Srivastava et al., 2015). Aqueous extract of tuber of <i>P. tuberosa</i> has further been reported to act as incretin receptor agonist and downregulated β-cells apoptosis and protected STZ-induced diabetes in rats^[9] (Srivastava et al., 2018).</p>
2	Sariva	<p>Quantitative evaluation of crude chemical components in <i>H. indicus</i> root extract gave the following results: Tannin 3.06%, saponin 12.55%, flavonoid 1.12%, alkaloid 1.23%, terpenoid 0.79%, coumarin 0.91% phenol 1.1%, the average amount of lupeol octacosanoate in root powder is 36.5 mg/g. <i>H. indicus</i> contains many biologically active compounds, including a new series of coumarino-lignans called hemidesmins, and steroidal glycosides called hemidesmosides A-C.^[10]</p>	<p>Antidiabetic activity Treatment with 2-hydroxy-4-methoxy benzoic acid resulted in the following effects in rats:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased activity of total ATPases, Na/K ATPase, Mg²⁺-ATPase, and Ca²⁺-ATPase. • Decreased levels of catalase, superoxide dismutase, glutathione peroxidase, and glutathione-S-transferase in erythrocytes. • Enhanced levels of vitamin E. • Lower levels of vitamin C and glutathione in both plasma and erythrocytes. Additionally, an active principle called β-amyryn palmitate was identified in root extract and was reported to have the potential for treating diabetes mellitus at low concentrations in diabetic rats induced by alloxan

			and streptozotocin. These findings suggest that 2-hydroxy-4-methoxy benzoic acid and β -amyrin palmitate may have potential therapeutic applications in the context of diabetes and oxidative stress. ^[11]
3	Rajani	Rubia cordifolia (Manjistha) basically known for its anthraquinones and naphthohydroquinones phytochemical constituents. The major phytoconstituents of Rubia cordifolia reported include Rubiadin ²⁷ , Rubicordone A ²⁸ , Rubiasins AC ²⁹ , Rubiatriol (triterpenoid), 6-methoxygeniposidic acid an iridoid glycoside ³⁰ and two pentacyclic triterpenoid- Rubicoumaric acid and Rubifolic acid ^{31,32} . Mollugin, furomollugin, dehydro-alpha-lapchone are isolated from chloroform fraction. ^[12]	Anti Diabetic Property: Effect of alcoholic extract of roots of Rubia cordifolia was studied on elevated blood glucose level in alloxan treated animals. The extract reduced the blood sugar level raised by alloxan. Alcoholic extract enhanced brain γ -amino-n-butyric acid (GABA) levels and decreased brain dopamine and plasma corticosterone levels. ^[13] Anti – diabetic activity: Manjistha has shown potential as an anti-diabetic agent by lowering blood sugar levels. It may work by enhancing insulin sensitivity and regulating glucose metabolism. The compound polyphenols and anthraquinon present in manjistha which helps in glucose metabolism through which blood sugar level balance. Inhibition of Alpha-Glucosidase Enzyme: Alpha-glucosidase is an enzyme that breaks down complex carbohydrates into glucose, leading to a rise in blood sugar levels after meals. Manjistha can naturally inhibit this enzyme, slowing carbohydrate breakdown and gradual glucose absorption. This helps prevent rapid spikes in blood sugar after eating, which can be especially beneficial for diabetic patients. ^[14]
4	Guduchi	Alkaloids= Berberine, Choline Palmatin, Tinosporine, Magnoflorine, Tembetarine, Anti-viral infections Stem root and Isocolumbin, Aporphine alkaloids, Jatrorrhizine, Tetrahydropalmatine. Miscellaneous compound= α ,4-	Anti-diabetic activity In a diabetic rat model, extracts from the root of guduchi have been shown to reduce brain mediated lipid levels and lower both blood and urinary glucose levels, underscoring their anti diabetic and lipid-lowering effects ³⁸ . The root extract of

		di hydroxyl-3 methoxybenzyl)-4-(4- Compounds hydroxyl-3-methoxy-benzyl)-tetrahydrofuran, Giloinin, Tinosporic acid, Tinosporidine, Cordifol, Cordifellone, Jatrorrhizine, Ntrans feruloyltyramineas diacetate. ^[15]	guduchi exhibits an antihyperglycemic effect in an alloxan-induced diabetic model by normalizing the elevated glucose levels found in both urine and blood ³⁹ . The anti-diabetic properties of <i>Tinospora cordifolia</i> , along with its active compound palmatine, primarily operate through an insulin-dependent pathway, while also enhancing the expression of Glut-4 and PPAR. Berberine, a close analogue of palmatine, has been demonstrated to exert its effects by facilitating Glut-4 translocation and increasing AMP-activated protein kinase (AMPK) activity in L6 myotubes, as well as modulating lipogenic genes to reduce lipid accumulation in 3T3-L1 cells ^[16]
5	Ajashrungi	Phytochemical Analysis The preliminary phytochemical screening study of <i>G. Sylvestre</i> root extract revealed the presence of alkaloids anthraquinones, Flavoids, Phenols, Steroids, Tannins and Terpenoids. The therapeutic effect of medicinal plant is due presence of these secondary products present in the plant. Phytochemical screening of <i>G. Sylvestre</i> root indicates that the plant is richest source of Phytochemicals like saponins, glycosides, tannins and flavonoids. Saponins and glycosides were found in higher concentrations but lower concentration of phenols, flavonoids, alkaloids, steroids were recorded. ^[17]	Antidiabetic Activity Administration of this plant in a diabetic animal model resulted in reductions in the blood levels of insulin, protein, triglycerides, cholesterol, and glucose, as well as a reduction in body weight and was found to improve liver histopathology. ^[18]

Therapeutic actions of Valli Panchamool Mishraka Gana

रक्तपित्तहरौ ह्येतौ शोफत्रय विनाशनौ |

सर्वमेहहरौ चैव शुक्रदोष विनाशनौ || सु.सू.३८

According to Acharya Sushrut, these all drugs mentioned in Valli panchamool are together effective in Raktapitta, Shopha, Meha and Shukradosha.

Mode of Action

Valli Panchamool effective in Raktapitta- Rakta along with vitiated Pitta oozing out of orifices is called as Raktapitta. Due to the Nidana Sevana when the Pitta gets vitiated, because of its Ushna Guna it leads to oozing out of liquid from Mamsadi Dhatus and this causes increase in the quantity of Drava Guna of Rakta and because of Ashraya and Ashrayi Bhavas, the Gunas of Pitta cannot be differentiated from the Rakta and Pitta becomes homologous with Rakta and due to the increased pressure because of Drava Guna the Rakta Dhatu starts oozing out of the orifices from Urdwa, Adho and Tiryak Marga. Hence depending upon the path of oozing out of blood it is classified as Urdhwaga, Adhoga and Tiryak/Ubhayaga Raktapitta.

Valli Panchamool's Dravya have Madhur, Tikta, Kashaya rasa which helps in Rakta prasadan. Sheeta veerya helps in Rakta stambhan. Sariva and Manjishtha are having gamitva towards Rakta dhatu. The combination helps in raktagat aamapachan, rakta prasadan, stambhan and balya.

Valli Panchamool Effective in Shopha-Tridosha get vitiated and in turn vitiate *Rakta Dhatu* and settle in *Raktavaha Srotas* i.e. Blood vessels, causing avarodha or obstruction in them. As a result *Doshas* get diverted (*Vimargagamana*) and start accumulating under the skin and muscle. Sariva and Manjishtha are helpful in rakta prasadan along with aamapachan.

Valli Panchamool effective in Meha- Dushit kleda is the main reason the samprapti of Meha which leads to polyuria. Drugs like Guduchi, meshashrunji helps in kelda pachan. Individual drugs mentioned in this combination are found to be effective in Meha (Diabetes mellitus) separately also.

Valli Panchamool effective in Shukra dosha- There are 8 types of Shukra dushti mentioned in various Ayurvedic texts. Drugs like Vidar, Sariva are having shukra gamitva and helps in different types of shukra dushti.

Dose- 2 to 3 grams with hot water.

DISCUSSION

The content of Valli panchamool Mishraka gana are Vidari, Sariva, Manjishtha, Guduchi and Ajashrunji. This dravyas have Tikta, Madhur, Kashaya Rasa, Katu Vipaka, Ushna Veerya and Guru, Snigdha Guna. Due to all properties it reduces the elevated Pitta Dosha, Kapha dosha and reduces obstruction in the Srotasa especially due to kleda. So it is useful in various Pitta and Kaphaj Diseases mainly occurred due to kleda dushti. Also various researches are done on the dravyas of Valli panchamoolj gana and Various Pharmacological actions of this dravyas are proven such as Anti-inflammatory, Anti diabetic, Hepatoprotective, Anti oxidant and so on.

CONCLUSION

It is Concluded that 'Valli Panchamool' One of the Mishrak Gana described by Acharya Sushruta have various therapeutic potential to reduces the various symptoms and diseases like Raktapitta, Shopha, Meha, Shukra dushti and so on by their Therapeutic Potential.

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